

MEDINA

Deliverable D7.2

Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Editor(s):	Ganbayar Uuganbayar, Artsiom Yautsiukhin
Responsible Partner:	CNR
Status-Version:	Final – v1.0
Date:	30.04.2021
Distribution level (CO, PU):	Public

Project Number:	952633
Project Title:	MEDINA

Title of Deliverable:	Dissemination and Communication strategy
Due Date of Delivery to the EC	30.04.2021

Work package responsible for the Deliverable:	WP7 - Dissemination and Training
Editor(s):	Ganbayar Uuganbayar, Artsiom Yautsiukhin (CNR)
Contributor(s):	Jesus Luna Garcia (BOSCH), Mika Leskinen (NIXU), Björn Fanta (FABASOFT), Leire Orue-Echevarria Arrieta (TECNALIA)
Reviewer(s):	Iñaki Etxaniz (TECNALIA)
Approved by:	All Partners
Recommended/mandatory readers:	Recommended for all WPs

Abstract:	<p>This deliverable presents a detailed and structured strategy for dissemination and communication of the MEDINA project. It outlines the objectives, target audience and plans to execute specific activities to achieve the related KPIs defined in the DoA.</p> <p>The dissemination strategy identifies and elaborates main activities to spread the knowledge about MEDINA's results in the scientific and commercial communities. These activities comprise scientific publications, seminars, courses, networking with various projects and organisations, participation in industrial events, etc. The communication strategy outlines the main means and their planned use to promote MEDINA. The identified activities involve all partners to maximise the effect.</p>
Keyword List:	Dissemination, communication, teaching, social media
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Document Description

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
v0.1	18.12.2020	Table of Contents. Draft	CNR
v0.5	10.04.2021	Comments and suggestions received by consortium partners	ALL
v0.8	15.04.2021	Completed the final version for internal review	CNR
v0.9	24.04.2021	Reviewer's comments are addressed	CNR, Tecnia, BOSCH
v0.9.5	27.04.2021	Additional comments addressed	CNR
v1.0	30.04.2021	Final modifications.	Tecnia

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Terms and abbreviations

CAB	Conformity Assessment Body
CSA or EU CSA	EU Cybersecurity Act
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
CISO	Chief Information Security Officer
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MOOC	Massive Open Online Courses
NCCA	National Certification Authority
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
OSCAL	Open Security Controls Assessment Language
TOM	Technical and Organizational Measure
EUCS	European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services

Executive summary

This deliverable (D7.2) describes the detailed strategy for spreading the main results of the MEDINA project. It outlines the objectives, target audiences, planned ways and means, as well as responsibilities of stakeholders for dissemination and communication activities.

The main objectives of MEDINA in this respect are to widely disseminate the project concept, development and findings; to ensure that all relevant communities and stakeholders are reached out; to create and publish scientific contributions among the research community; to collaborate with other projects, ENISA, or national bodies recognizing the certification activities. To address all these objectives, target audiences have been defined and classified in a first step, to later outline specific messages for each of them. MEDINA partners will contribute to communication and dissemination activities, depending on their capability. Roles has been assigned, having each defined activity a partner with the leader role.

The deliverable comprises two main sections: dissemination and communication. The dissemination activities are to be performed targeting both scientific and industrial community. Dissemination activities cover publishing scientific results in top journals and conferences and collaborating with different projects. Scientific events, including seminars, workshops and teaching, will further be considered by the partners in order to spread the results of MEDINA. For dissemination of results in the industrial community, partners will present their results through related events to various communities in different countries.

The planned communication strategy for the project identifies various sources of communication media to share and deliver the information about the project to target communities and general public. A digital strategy based in inbound marketing is defined, comprising four main steps: attract, convert, close and delight visitors. A list of communications means to reach stakeholders is presented -e.g. website, blog, brochures, newsletters, white papers, etc.-, providing for each of them specific objectives, key messages, providers, targets and other elements to define the required communication.

For communication and dissemination, a set of KPIs to be achieved with the described strategy is shown. The monitoring activity includes tools like Google Analytics, Twitter Analytics, monthly reports (see several form templates in the appendix). The effort and results will be monitored on a monthly basis, which will allow obtaining an up-to-date picture of the performance and, if required, timely plan corrective measures.

This deliverable will be further used as guidelines by the MEDINA partners in their dissemination and communication effort. All these activities to implement the strategy will be further reported in D7.4 and D7.5 (Dissemination and Communications Report v1 and v2), to report the achieved results towards the defined KPIs.

1 Introduction

MEDINA partners fully understand the importance of spreading the knowledge about the project and are fully committed to contribute to various dissemination and communication activities. The initial goals for these activities have been outlined in the DoA. This deliverable provides more detailed and up-to-date information about how the partners are planning to achieve the defined goals.

1.1 About this deliverable

The main goal of this deliverable is to introduce the dissemination and communication strategy which describes how the goals for dissemination and communication will be achieved. The document starts with elaboration of goals for dissemination and communication activities. These activities are planned to be performed in three phases with different objectives, depending on the state of the project and readiness of its results. In order to focus the effort, the partners have identified target communities and roles they play in the identified activities.

The core of the deliverable is a structured walk-through of the dissemination and communication strategy. The dissemination strategy is defined for both Scientific and Commercial community. The main activities for scientific dissemination identified are networking with other projects, publication in conference proceedings and journals, and organising courses and providing supporting materials. The main activities for commercial dissemination are as follows: participation in industrial events and exhibits, giving seminars, collaborating with relevant associations, presenting project posters and taking parts in standardization-related activities. The communication is to be performed with such means as a project web site, brochures, press releases, blog posts, project newsletter, white papers, project showcases and social networks (Twitter, Slideshare, YouTube).

The content of this deliverable will be used by partners to guide their dissemination and communication effort and the results of this effort will be reported in D7.4 and D7.5 (Dissemination and Communications Report v1 and v2).

1.2 Document structure

The deliverable is structured as follows. First, the objectives for dissemination and communication and the target audience are identified in Section 2. Section 3 provides the dissemination strategy plan, splitting the activities targeting scientific and commercial communities. After that, communication strategy is described in Section 4, providing details for all implemented and planned communication means. Conclusion (Section 5) ends the deliverable.

2 Objectives

The main objective of this deliverable is to present a strategy for the project in order to efficiently disseminate of its results and communicate with various parties. It comprises awareness program, scientific publications, organised events for industrial, certification, scientific, and general public bodies.

The dissemination and communication activities are planned to be executed in the following three phases (according to DoA [2]):

- **Awareness creation (M1-M6).** During this phase, the project has established various communication channels (see Section 4 for details) and created a Dissemination and Communication Strategy presented in this deliverable. Furthermore, the partners have made the first steps to present the project and establish required connections for the further collaboration (e.g., with ENISA, GAIA-X, OSCAL, etc.), participating in various events and publishing some papers on topics related to MEDINA. These achievements will be reported in detail by D7.4 Dissemination and Communication v1.
- **Delivery (M7-M30)** is the next and the longest phase during which the project will perform all types of activities to spread the knowledge about MEDINA and disseminate its results. There are two sub-phases, split by the first Dissemination and Communication report (D7.4):
 - M7-M18: We envisage a slow start with respect to dissemination activities (especially, relevant publications or demonstrations) as the main results are to be yet developed by the participants. Nevertheless, the project will continue enlarging its network of contacts, participating in various events and promoting its brand. Moreover, the established communication means will be fully operational.
 - M19-M30: The situation will change as the project progresses and more achievements will be available for dissemination. Many results will be still disseminated in isolation, depending on the time they are achieved. This fragmentation of the disseminated knowledge will help to publicize these results early and attract attention of various audiences to the future and more comprehensive achievements of MEDINA.
- **Final (M31-M36+).** At this final stage all results of MEDINA will be finalized, solidified, and integrated. The project will be able to promote the overall MEDINA platform and demonstrate its operation. Next to the holistic picture, some fragmented results of the project will continue being disseminated for very targeted audience (e.g., publications). In short, the project expects to have high number of results to communicate to various audiences at this phase, providing complete and mature results. The network established in the previous phases will be fully exploited to maximize the outreach.

2.1 Dissemination and communication objectives

According to the DoA [2], the focus of dissemination and communication is:

- To create awareness among CSPs, auditors, certification authorities, certification bodies, ENISA, industrial associations and cloud consumers;
- To communicate the results of the project among the technical and scientific community to improve the access to relevant research communities;
- To seek cooperation with ENISA, national accreditation bodies and agencies in charge of recognizing the certification activities.

In particular, MEDINA aims:

- To widely disseminate and communicate the project concept, developments and findings to identified stakeholders using effective communication means and strategies.
- To ensure that all relevant communities will be reached out to in an interactive way, integrating their feedback at key timestamps of the project: namely specification requirements, market analysis, design, development and evaluation periods, as well as during exploitation tasks.
- To create and publish scientific contributions valuable for the research community.
- To collaborate with other European projects in the relevant topics of MEDINA.
- To participate in appropriate European and worldwide events (workshops, seminars, conferences, etc.) targeted at industry and academia with the ultimate goal not only to showcase MEDINA results and subsequently to prepare the way for a successful commercial exploitation of the project outcomes, but also to create a MEDINA community mobilizing its members whenever it is needed (requirements definition process, evaluation period, etc....).
- To address the future adoption and ensure the sustainability of the project results taking into account the market trends, the business scenarios and the consortium and partners' needs and strategies. This overall objective will be pursued defining, and managing, a consistent and synergic strategy structured around specific analysis and exploitation activities.

2.2 Target audience

This section aims to define the main audiences for dissemination and communication activities.

CSPs including CISOs and compliance managers

The biggest target audience of the MEDINA framework are CSPs, and especially small CSPs that do not have the adequate tools to automate the monitoring of the compliance of the controls defined as “high” assurance level in the EUCS. However, since the EUCS is incremental, both in the requirements' perspective as well as in the conformity assessment actions, MEDINA can also help CSPs that aim to get certified in basic and substantial.

Conformity Assessment Bodies (CABs), Auditors, National Certification Authorities (NCCA)

The second big type of audience is the stakeholders involved in the conformity assessment bodies, be them the CABs themselves, the auditors or the NCCAs. In principle, not all components of the MEDINA framework will be useful, or even usable, for this kind of stakeholders. Out of the current envisioned modules envisioned, the ones interesting for these stakeholders are the ones that collect, store and assess the evidences. For this reason, it is key that they trust the tools that collect these evidences and are sure that these have not been manipulated at any stage of the process.

Research & Technical security community

Research and technical security community is interested in the cutting-edge research and innovation ideas in the security field. This community demands for in-depth description of and early access to the novel ideas and achievements. MEDINA faces several research problems, solutions for which will be disseminated to this community.

ENISA, national authorities and other policy-makers

ENISA is the agency in charge of the development and follow up of the EUCS. MEDINA is up to the knowledge of the consortium, the first solution that addresses the automated monitoring aspects required in the scheme.

it is important to raise awareness about cloud security certification among national authorities and policy makers to help them to correctly perceive the current state of technology. This knowledge could be further used in up-to-date legislations and policies.

Working groups and associations

MEDINA will promote itself and its results in the working groups and associations where major public cloud providers, national certification bodies and European cloud customers participate.

General public and cloud service users

General Public refers to all people not included in previous groups. They can be anyway interested in certification, security and cloud.

2.3 Partner's role in summary

MEDINA partners will be contributing to dissemination and communication activities with their full capabilities. Each partner is responsible for a different task depending on their capability. Furthermore, partners should nominate a person in charge for each dissemination and communication activity. The following shows the highlighted responsibilities by the partners.

Table 1. Partners' role

	CNR	NIXU	BOSCH	HPE	TECNALIA	Fabasoft	XLAB	FhG
Collaboration with other projects	L	C	C	C	C	C	C	C
Conferences and Journals	L	C	C	C	C	C	C	C
Seminars	C	C	L	C	C	C	C	C
Teaching	L	C	C	C	C	C	C	C
Participation in Industrial events	C	C	L	C	C	C	C	C
Exhibits	C	C	L	C	C	C	C	C
Consumer and Industrial Associations	C	C	L	C	C	C	C	C
Project Posters	C	C	C	C	C	L	C	C
Standardization-related activities	C	C	L	C	C	C	C	C
Website	C	C	C	C	L	C	C	C
Brochures	C	C	C	C	L	C	C	C
Press Releases	C	C	C	C	C	L	C	C
Blog Posts	C	L	C	C	C	C	C	C
Project Newsletters	C	C	C	C	C	L	C	C
White papers	C	L	C	C	C	C	C	C
Project Showcases	C	C	C	C	L	C	C	C
Social Media	C	C	C	C	L	C	C	C

C = Contributor, L = Leader

3 Dissemination

This section addresses various approaches planned by MEDINA to disseminate its results. Specific actions are planned for Scientific and Commercial communities.

3.1 Messages to communicate

The DoA [2] has already defined the key messages to the target audiences (see Section 2.2). Here we elaborate and refine them.

CSPs including CISOs and compliance managers

- The MEDINA framework selects the most relevant TOMs to ensure compliance with the selected cloud security control framework and achieve the required assurance level (if such is defined by the cloud security control framework).
- The MEDINA framework is able to significantly reduce the effort and expenses for compliance maintenance by continuous compliance monitoring.
- The evidences collected by the framework are controlled by the CSP but can be easily provided to and be trusted by a conformity assessment body.
- The MEDINA framework is able to verify compliance with several cloud security control frameworks, switching between them if required, and re-using the evidences collected for one security control framework in another one (e.g., BSI C5 and EUCS). This should significantly reduce the effort, time and cost if several certifications must be obtained.
- The MEDINA framework is able to integrate new cloud security control frameworks (and update the existing ones with new versions) by transforming them semi-automatically into a machine-readable certification representation to be further used by MEDINA.
- The MEDINA framework supports various service delivery models (IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS).

Conformity Assessment Bodies (CABs), Auditors, National Certification Authorities (NCCA)

- How the repository of TOMs is used for cloud certification.
- The MEDINA framework is able to collect evidences and make them available for external evaluation (also by different auditors).
- The MEDINA framework will continuously evaluate the current status of the CSP's compliance with a security control framework and detect deviations.
- The detected deviations are automatically ranked, and relevant corrective actions are assigned (e.g., a warning is sent if major deviation is detected).
- The collected evidences are collected by the CSP but can be trusted by external evaluators.
- The MEDINA framework supports compliance verification for various types of CSPs (IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS).

Research & Technical security community

- The possibility to semi-automatically translate a security control framework written in a natural language into a machine-readable format.
- Risk-based assessment approach for (cloud) security certification.
- Automatic, continuous and evidence-supported compliance verification.

ENISA, national authorities and other policymakers

- The MEDINA framework is able to continuously verify compliance to the EU-wide cloud security control framework.
- The MEDINA framework supports risk-based and evidence-supported auditing against the EU-wide cloud security control framework.

Working groups, associations and general public

- The compliance verification with the MEDINA framework can be trusted by customers.
- The declared level of assurance (basic, substantial, and high) can be guaranteed.

3.2 Information to be disseminated

The MEDINA project contains seven work packages with deliverables and additional materials to disseminate. The information to be delivered is classified into either public or internal depending on its sensitivity and restriction. Internal information is shared in a dedicated cloud environment. Public information will be communicated to the general public through several means defined by the project, like project website, social media, blogs, as well as through publicly organised events. The following table shows the overview of the information which MEDINA projects initially intends to disseminate and their vehicle to share:

Table 2. Information to be disseminated

ID	Title
D2.1	Continuously certifiable technical and organizational measures and catalogue of cloud security metrics
D2.3	Specification of the Cloud Security Certification Language
D2.6	Risk-based techniques and tools for Cloud Security Certification
D3.1	Tools and techniques for the management of trustworthy evidence
D3.4	Tools and techniques for collecting evidence of technical and organisational measures
D4.1	Tools and techniques for the management and evaluation of cloud security certifications
D4.4	Methodology and tools for risk-based assessment and security control reconfiguration
D5.1	MEDINA Requirements, Detailed architecture, DevOps infrastructure and CI/ CD and verification strategy
D5.3	MEDINA integrated solution
D7.1	MEDINA public website
D7.1	MEDINA brochure
D7.2	Dissemination and Communication Strategy
D7.3	Market, Innovation and Applicability Analysis
D7.4	Dissemination and Communication Report
D7.8	Standardization Roadmap
D7.10	Training materials
-	Workshop materials
-	White papers
-	Press releases
-	Newsletters and Blog posts

3.3 Scientific dissemination

The main dissemination activity planned to disseminate MEDINA's results in scientific community is to publish these results in top conferences proceedings and journals. This activity will be led by CNR to encourage the partners to publish high quality papers, deliver dedicated talks and organizing different scientific events, such as workshops and seminars. Also, collaborations with other projects will be launched to identify synergies and amplify mutual impact on the scientific community.

Also, collaboration with other projects will be one of the main plans in this part as some partners already started working on a “Participation in Cloud Consultation” topic with ENISA AdHoc WG on Cloud Security project. The following sub-sections will discuss more in detail.

3.3.1 Collaboration with other projects

MEDINA understands networking as the activities that involve initiatives as well as liaison and co-operation actions with other projects.

The objectives of the networking activities are:

- Exploit synergies with other projects and initiatives that have common aspects with MEDINA.
- Coordinate joint activities for dissemination and exploitation.

All MEDINA partners will contribute to networking activities. They can range from publishing a joint paper with another project, to contribute to a standard or participate in concertation meetings organized by the European Commission.

MEDINA has identified already a set of projects, mainly coming from the same objective as MEDINA, with which a collaboration can be interesting, so that bilateral and multilateral meetings and discussions can start. Some related activities have already started, and initial collaborations are on-going (e.g., cooperation with GAIA-X or ENISA AdHoc WGs). The goal for these discussions and meetings is initially to explore common or complementary aspects, but that can evolve into a more stable collaboration.

The following table shows the potential initiatives and projects related to MEDINA.

Table 3. Identified initiatives with whom MEDINA can collaborate

Initiative	Objective and scope	Potential areas of collaboration	Status
GAIA-X Working Group Continuous monitoring	GAIA-X is developing the foundations for a federated, open data infrastructure based on European values.	Catalogue of metrics, evidence management tools, continuous evaluation tools	On-going
NIST OSCAL	NIST is developing the Open Security Controls Assessment Language (OSCAL). OSCAL provides machine-readable representations of control catalogs, control baselines, system security plans, and assessment plans and results.	Continuous evaluation tools	Started
ENISA European Cloud Services Certification scheme (EUCS)	ENISA is the European Agency in charge of the definition and maintenance of the European Cloud Services Certification scheme designed under the European Cybersecurity Act.	All aspects but especially the feasibility of the requirements with assurance level high. Also, the notion of continuous certification	On-going

Initiative	Objective and scope	Potential areas of collaboration	Status
IOTAC 1.09.2020 – 30.08.2023	IOTAC aims to deliver a new, secure and privacy-friendly Internet of Things (IoT) architecture enabling the development and operation of more resilient IoT service environments. This can be done by monitoring and evaluating applications security throughout the broader software development life cycle.	Evidence management tools	Started
CYRENE 1.10.2020 – 30.09.2023	CYRENE aims to enhance the security, privacy, resilience, accountability and trustworthiness of supply chains, through the provision of a novel and dynamic Conformity Assessment Process (CAP) that evaluates the security and resilience of SC services	Compositional certification	Not started
PIACERE 1.12.2020 – 30.11.2023	PIACERE aims to develop tools, techniques and methods to allow organisations to develop and operate IaC through DevSecOps practices as they would do with traditional code, with a special focus on trustworthiness and security aspects throughout the IaC life cycle.	Evidence management tools (Vulnerability assessment)	Started
H2020 SPARTA 1.12.2020 – 30.11.2023	The SPARTA brings together a unique set of actors at the intersection of scientific excellence, technological innovation, and societal sciences in cybersecurity. Among other activities, it runs 4 scientific programs.	New perspective of co-operation and integration with Cloud environment and advancements in security certification (CAPE program).	Started
HUB4CLOUD 1.01.2021 – 30.06.2022	HUB4CLOUD will assist growing the impact and relevance of Cloud Computing research, innovation and policy-driven efforts, while accelerating its adoption and deployments in Europe. By running dedicated coordination and support	(Continuous) Cloud certification topic	Started

Initiative	Objective and scope	Potential areas of collaboration	Status
	activities, including roadmapping, dissemination, organisation of events, mapping of open source/(pre-)standardisation initiatives, and business acceleration activities, HUB4CLOUD will ensure the creation of an open, inclusive, and sustainable ecosystem.		
SWForum.eu 1.10.2021 – 31.03.2023	SWForum.eu project will work to raise awareness and strengthen the competitive advantage of the European software industry. It will foster a sustainable European forum for stakeholders representing scientific researchers, providers, developers, operators and policymakers linked to software technologies, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity. In addition to the forum, the project will also organise workshops, a platform to share experiences and research, and innovation road maps for European Commission policy officers and stakeholders.	Software Engineering for the Cloud, Digital infrastructures certification, C cybersecurity and DLT	Started

While the previous table lists the initiatives and projects and the status of the collaboration, the following table reports such collaboration on various dimensions, namely type, level and degree. These dimensions have proven to be useful in other projects¹ in order to plan the follow-up activities. They are explained next:

- Type of collaboration:
 - Technical: common results or reuse each other's results
 - Promotional: to participate or organize joint events or workshops, joint publications and so on.
 - Commercial: joint exploitation, but always with an agreement.
- Level of collaboration:
 - Project level: the collaboration between MEDINA and another research projects.
 - Organization level: collaboration with an organization on a one-to-one level.

¹ For example, in the DECIDE H2020 project

- Interest Group level: the collaboration is established with an SDO, executive agency, other initiatives
- Degree of collaboration:
 - Continuous: continuous collaboration.
 - Frequent: from time to time, but without a plan
 - Punctual: isolated collaboration.

The following table classifies the collaboration in agreement with the categories above. The legend of colours is as follows: **Continuous** collaboration is shown in green, **frequent** collaboration in blue and **punctual** collaboration in red.

Table 4. Collaboration classification

Collaboration Type	Collaboration level		
	Project	Organization	Interest Group
Technical	PIACERE, IOTAC, CYREBE, SPARTA, HUB4CLOUD, SWForum.eu	Not defined	NIST OSCAL, GAIA-X, ENISA (EUCS)
Promotional	SPARTA	Not defined	Not defined
Commercial	Not defined	Not defined	Not defined

This list will be continuously updated throughout the course of the project.

3.3.2 Conferences and journals

The core of scientific dissemination is to publish high quality papers in proceedings of top conferences and journals. To that end, MEDINA partners, particularly CNR, are committed to contribute to presenting the results to well-known journal and conferences. MEDINA encourages all partners to be involved to disseminate the results individually as well as publish joint papers. MEDINA intends to reach at least 15 conference papers during the project. Some targeted conferences are listed as follows and the list will be continuously updated:

Table 5. Initially identified conferences

Conference Name	Expected period	Link	Status
IFIP SEC	2021-2024	https://ifipsec.org/	Not Started
ERCIM STM	2021-2024	https://www.ercim.eu/	Not Started
JOWUA	2021-2024	http://jowua.com/	Not Started
Cert	2021-2024	https://nationalcert.org/events/2021-national-conference	Not Started
IEEE CLOUD	2021-2024	https://conferences.computer.org/cloud/	Not Started
QUATIC	2021-2024	https://2021.quatic.org/	Not started

Also, NIXU will leverage from existing invites to contribute various conferences and events in Finland, Sweden and Denmark.

MEDINA acknowledges that scientific results at top journal can reach more scientific communities and realizes its impact. The following journals are found to be applicable targets in the final years of the project:

Table 6. Targeted journals

Journal Name	Expected period	Link	Status
Computers & Security	2023-2024	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/computers-and-security	Not Started
IJIS	2023-2024	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/1098111x	Not Started
FGCS	2023-2024	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/future-generation-computer-systems	Not Started
Journal of Systems and software	2021-2023	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-systems-and-software	Not Started

Benefits of publishing papers at conferences and journals can be seen as:

- Reaching different targets through published papers
- Continuous discussions with experts and researchers
- Continuous improvement based on comments from experts
- Co-operation with various researchers

3.3.3 Teaching

MEDINA project partners foresee to be involved at least 4 training courses in the last year of the project including Winter and Summer schools. It plans to organize 2 courses in the following venues:

- The International School on Foundations of Security Analysis and Design (FOSAD): has been one of the foremost events established with the goal of disseminating knowledge in this critical area since the first even in 2000. The main aim of the FOSAD school is to offer a good spectrum of current research in foundations of security - ranging from programming languages to analysis of protocols, from cryptographic algorithms to access control policies and trust management - that can be of help for graduate students and young researchers from academia or industry that intend to approach the field.
- The European Network for Cybersecurity (NeCS) PhD School was launched four years ago, in response to the increase need of highly qualified experts in cyber-security. The School addresses the issues of training and development of talented junior researchers as indicated in the European Cybersecurity strategy and highlighted in the EC's Digital Agenda.

Moreover, MEDINA partners plan to provide 2 online courses (MOOCs) on the topics related to the project. In this regard, partners also will put some of suitable results into a format for online courses so that others could benefit from it and get aware about MEDINA project and its achievements.

3.4 Commercial dissemination

Commercial dissemination is a central part of the whole plan to share MEDINA's results. MEDINA's industrial partners (Bosch, NIXU, Fabasoft, and HPE) are the leaders for the commercial dissemination while the other partners also further contribute to their effort. This section identifies the following activities to disseminate the results to the industrial community.

3.4.1 Participation in industrial events

MEDINA partners aim at participating relevant industrial events similar to NetFutures, ICT Event, CloudExpo, CEBIT, Gartner Security and Risk Management Summit, and Information Security Solutions Europe Conferences. Also, Bosch-sponsored events (mostly online due to COVID) target network of developers (approx. 5K), corporate research community (approx. 3K) and IT auditors (approx. 1K). Example of relevant external events where Bosch participates are AWS Re:inforce (AWS security), Microsoft Ignite (Microsoft), and more recently those organized by clusters of H2020 projects (e.g., CONCORDIA, CYBERSEC4EU, ECHO and SPARTA).

3.4.2 Exhibits

Exhibits are the potential targets that MEDINA partners aim at disseminating the results through attending and presenting at the exhibits. MEDINA partners foresee the following exhibits as targets:

- Fabasoft aims at disseminating the results at the ETSI Security Week². This will be done approx. 2022 and / or 2023 via a Poster Presentation (see below) and / or participation at the call for papers
- Fabasoft will disseminate project results focused around Use Case 2 at its own sponsored events or webinars, if the topic is connected to "cybersecurity".
- Bosch will present the projects' results and general progress in own events (e.g., Bosch Connected World³), and also in those where the MEDINA topic is relevant (including Microsoft Ignite⁴, and AWS Re:inForce⁵). Our expectation is to distribute leaflets and

² Please refer to <https://www.etsi.org/events/1653-etsi-security-week-2020>

³ Please refer to <https://bosch-connected-world.com/>

⁴ Please refer to <https://myignite.microsoft.com/>

⁵ Please refer to <https://reinforce.awsevents.com/>

one-pagers related to MEDINA, and (when available) to show the project's use cases in sessions organized for relevant audiences.

- HPE will present for CyberTech Europe
- Fraunhofer regularly presents at the Hannover Fair, IT-SA or other German-based events
- NIXU will cover the area around Denmark, Finland, Netherlands and Sweden
- TECNALIA will use their marketing service in Spain and the Basque Country

3.4.3 Seminars

Seminars are another alternative to disseminate the results and attract different bodies. MEDINA partners intend to present how specific tools work and conduct guided presentations. For instance, Bosch will present MEDINA in its internal seminars aiming cloud/IoT developers, security architects, and governance teams worldwide. Such seminars will be organized remotely in order to cover bigger audience and will provide hands-on tutorials in particular for cloud certification relevant roles (e.g., EUCS), auditors and product/service owners).

3.4.4 Consumer and industrial associations

MEDINA will also create an engagement with consumer/industrial associations in Europe where Bosch is member of e.g., Bitkom⁶, CSSA⁷, VDA⁸ and Digital Europe⁹. In particular, Bosch will continuously promote and participate in dissemination activities related to EUCS, where MEDINA is expected to have a major impact. Take for example the ongoing discussions within Bitkom and Digital Europe related to ENISA EUCS draft, and its public consultation, where Bosch target to disseminate MEDINA's outcomes on the topic of automated monitoring for high-assurance certifications. We foresee similar discussions in the context of VDA, where MEDINA/EUCS will have a relevant role in compositional certification with respect to TISAX¹⁰.

3.4.5 Project posters

Project posters are alternative methods defined by MEDINA consortium to disseminate results to different targets. In this regard, Fabasoft aims at presenting different key parts of their use case from WP6 (Use Case 2) in Poster Presentation Sessions. The produced material consists of plotted posters, demonstrating different developing steps of the use case, the Fabasoft Demo-System and the connectors (APIs) to the MEDINA Framework and will demonstrate the MEDINA feasibility from a CSP point of view.

Currently Fabasoft plans to produce at least three such posters (each for every project year):

1. Definition of the use case and high-level abstraction including the connection to personas and user stories (2021)
2. Story boards and wireframes – enriched by user story progression (2022)
3. Demo-System Screenshots and proof-of-work with selected Security Controls within MEDINA (2023)

The dissemination of Poster Presentations is chosen, as this is an established way of presenting such results and findings in different international conference throughout Europe. The targeted events or venues will be selected throughout the project lifetime and will be in line with events Fabasoft usually participates in, e.g., NetFutures, EU Commission ICT conference, B2B Software Days Vienna or selected ETSI events like the Security Week.

⁶ Please refer to <https://www.bitkom.org/>

⁷ Please refer to <https://www.cssa.de/en/index.html>

⁸ Please refer to <https://www.vda.de/en>

⁹ Please refer to <https://www.digitaleurope.org/>

¹⁰ Please refer to <https://portal.enx.com/en-US/TISAX/>

3.4.6 Standardization-related activities

Standardization activities in MEDINA are a topic by itself, however they also contribute to the dissemination/awareness activities related to the outcomes of the project. In such context, Bosch is leading the development of a standardization roadmap in MEDINA with the purpose of identifying the framework's components which need to be discussed within standards development organizations (SDO) in order to contribute towards MEDINA's sustainability. One example of such activities (already initiated during M1-M6) is the machine-readable representation of metrics/controls (WP2), which has already started with the US NIST's OSCAL¹¹ team. Such discussions are indirectly resulting in dissemination activities (see participation in OSCAL Workshop reported in Section 3.1), which we foresee will continue during the rest of MEDINA's duration.

The standardization roadmap's development also foresees interactions with relevant EU initiatives namely the ENISA AdHoc WG developing EUCS, where Bosch and Tecnia participate on behalf of MEDINA. From a dissemination point of view, such participation guarantees that other stakeholders (also part of the ENISA working group) became also aware of MEDINA and its value proposition towards EUCS. In this context is also worth to mention Gaia-X, where active participation exists from MEDINA-side (partners Fraunhofer, Tecnia, Fabasoft, and Bosch) and dissemination of our projects' activities is continuously taking place.

3.5 Dissemination assessment and evaluation

The dissemination and teaching effort will be monitored on a monthly basis. This frequency will allow the leaders of the corresponding activities and tasks to obtain the most up-to-date picture of the dissemination performance and timely plan corrective measures if required. The monitoring is to be performed by declaring the performed activity or a published paper using the defined forms (See Appendix, Section 7) and sharing them with other partners through the official collaboration means of MEDINA. The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and their target values for dissemination activities have been defined in the DoA and will be reported in the deliverables D7.4 and D7.5 (Dissemination and Communication Reports v1 and v2). To keep this deliverable self-contained, we add the table with KPIs for dissemination from DoA below.

Table 7. Dissemination KPIs (source: DoA)

Diss. tool	KPI	Objective	Contingency plans
Brochures	Number of leaflets / brochures produced	>3	Specific dissemination and communication WP defined where the production and management of the dissemination material such as the brochures is considered.
Conference / Journal publications	Number of publications Scientific journals Scientific conferences	2 15	Encourage partners to publish papers. Find appropriate events. Contact publishers of peer-reviewed and indexed journals. Search for additional channels.
Project posters	Number of posters	At least 3	Encourage partners to publish posters. Find appropriate events such as NetFutures, ICT Event, or CloudExpo among others.
Press releases	Number of specialized press releases	2 per country and language	The specific plan for communication will define the way in which the different communities (scientific, commercial,

¹¹ Please refer to <https://pages.nist.gov/OSCAL/>

Diss. tool	KPI	Objective	Contingency plans
			general public) will be targeted, as well as the social media will be used.
Project showcases	Number of different demonstration videos produced	10	Every time that a prototype is implemented as part of the MEDINA solution, the possibility of creating a video showing it will be considered.
Project newsletters	Number of newsletters	1 per year	The development of the project newsletter will be included in the specific MEDINA communication plan.
Attendance at industry-focused events	Number of events attended	5 per year	The potential key events interesting for MEDINA will be monitored and reported in every dissemination report. Here events similar to NetFutures, ICT event, CloudExpo, CEBIT, Gartner Security and Risk Management Summit, and Information Security Solutions Europe Conference will be targeted.
Whitepapers	Number of whitepapers published	2 per year	To complement the presentations at industry fairs, the consortium will prepare whitepapers and publish them on the project website, social media, and distribute it through domain related channels of high frequency.
Cloud Community, Software and Services Publications	Number of references in external magazines (Collaboration and Support Actions, EC)	+20	The scientific community, commercial stakeholders and the general public will be the target groups of the communication activities. The references to the MEDINA project will be monitored and checked every 6 months in order to fulfil the required KPI.
Courses / Capacity building	Number of training activities delivered	4	Encourage partners to put together the results into MOOCs or any other platforms as soon as such results have proven its added value.

4 Communication

The European Commission describes communication as:

“Communication means taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The aim is to reach out to society as a whole and in particular to some specific audiences while demonstrating how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.” [1]

In order to be successful in communication, MEDINA will use different channels. On one hand, the communication activities will rely on one channel communication measures such as the website, the blog or the newspapers. On the other hand, MEDINA will rely on a two-way communication where different stakeholders can interact with the project activities, mainly through the use of social networks, following a focused digital strategy.

4.1 Messages to communicate

This section aims to define the main messages to be delivered to the target audience (identified in Section 2.2).

CSPs including CISOs and compliance managers

- A greater efficiency in getting certified and (re-)certified
- End-to-end guidance on how to fulfil the EUCS security requirements and the key aspects that auditors may be looking at
- Automatic collection of evidences and automated monitoring of technical and organizational measures, applying the necessary assessment rules that will ensure that the security requirements implemented remain compliant.
- Assurance that the evidences collected have not been tampered with nor manipulated, so as to generate trust for the auditors, CABs and NCCA.
- Education towards the notion of “continuous certification”, concept not yet fully covered by the EUCS.

Conformity Assessment Bodies (CABs), Auditors, National Certification Authorities (NCCA)

- Trust in the tools that collect the evidences
- Trust that neither a tool nor a human can manipulate or tamper a collected evidence
- Trust in the tools that perform the automatic the assessment of the evidences
- Guidance for the evidence-based assessment but also for the other assurance levels
- Education towards the notion of “continuous certification”, concept not yet fully covered by the EUCS

ENISA

- Share the challenges faced by a CSP when seeking to achieve the assurance level high, especially in what respects the automated monitoring activities
- Share the lessons learned from a very first implementation of the EUCS in real CSPs
- Share an initial implementation of what “continuous certification” / “continuous auditing” is as well as the challenges for all involved stakeholders

General public and cloud service users

- MEDINA is a secure, trustable tool to certify cloud services and providers.
- MEDINA is a valuable tool that can help you deciding which service to contract.

4.2 Communication means

This section outlines the communication means that will be used in MEDINA to reach the identified stakeholders. For each of the means identified, the following aspects are detailed:

- **Objective:** what the objective of this communication tool is, what will the project communicate
- **Key Message/Content:** what is the key message that should be promoted
- **Target Stakeholder:** who is the target stakeholder that this communication mean focuses on.
- **Information Required & Level of Detail:** what information will be included, language in which it will be written, and whether it will be detailed (e.g. for technical audiences) or easier to understand (e.g. for non-technical audiences or less specialized)
- **Information Providers:** which partner within the consortium will be responsible for it
- **Communication Methods:** language
- **Activity Required for Production & Delivery:** is it online or paper?
- **Frequency & Timing:** how often this communication activity will be done
- **Feedback and Follow Up Activity:** how the content may be improved (e.g. through the feedback of readers, visitors, etc.)

4.2.1 Web site

The website of MEDINA has a twofold goal. On one hand, it will be used for short, targeted messages, presenting the project and the activities in a friendly manner. On the other hand, it will be used as a platform to share the project's results such as deliverables, communication materials, open source software and other. The look and feel of the website has been presented in D7.1 [3].

The website will be continuously updated as the project evolves. The following table summarizes the main characteristics of the MEDINA website¹²:

¹² <https://www.meditina-project.eu>

Table 8. Main characteristics of the MEDINA website

Characteristics	Description
Objective	Provide information about the project with different levels of detail
Key Message/Content	The mission of MEDINA, the solution, results (documents and software), approach, objectives and use cases. It will also include blog posts coming from the partners, participation in events, networking activities and so on.
Target Stakeholder	Researchers, technology providers, CSPs, CISOs, compliance managers, CABs, NCCA, ENISA
Information Required & Level of Detail	Written in English. Different levels of detail in the information. While most of the website is written in a user-friendly way with short focused content, the blog posts for instance may be much more detailed and deeper. For an in-depth information of MEDINA, the viewers can even check the public deliverables that will be released on a dedicated page on the website.
Information Providers	All partners
Communication Methods	English
Activity Required for Production & Delivery	Online
Frequency & Timing	News and blog posts will be updated on a regular basis. Other content shall be uploaded as soon as it becomes available.
Feedback and Follow Up Activity	Feedback from visitors and partners, KPIs coming from Google analytics tools.

4.2.2 Brochures

The brochure aims to create awareness of the project and provide short, on topic information to be distributed initially in events and fairs. Several versions of the brochure will be released in the timeframe of the project with different foci, such as the use cases and the results.

The structure of the brochure can be found in D7.1 [3]. The following table summarizes the main characteristics of the MEDINA Brochure.

Table 9. Main characteristics of the MEDINA brochure

Characteristics	Description
Objective	To be distributed in conferences, workshops and any kind of face to face events. Since at the time of writing this deliverable, no events are organized the brochure will be made available on the website and other means (e.g. social networks).
Key Message/Content	Briefly present different key aspects of MEDINA
Target Stakeholder	Visitors to conferences and events. Anyone visiting the MEDINA website
Information Required & Level of Detail	2 pages (+ front and cover). Easy to understand. For a wider community
Information Providers	All partners
Communication Methods	No specific configurations – Written in the English language. brochure will also be available on the website for downloading, and on SlideShare.

Characteristics	Description
Activity Required for Production & Delivery	Paper and online
Frequency & Timing	Not aligned with project's milestones. Agreed as the project evolves, and results are available. At least three.
Feedback and Follow Up Activity	Get remarks from the audience and make changes accordingly

4.2.3 Press releases

Press releases can be played as a vital tool to reach out various targets. MEDINA defines two main targets, non-technical (general public) and technical-oriented (e.g., CISOs). MEDINA aims to deliver at least two press releases per each country where a partner is located. Through the press releases, MEDINA plans to receive feedback from various targets, attract others and, most importantly, continuously improve the solution.

Table 10. Main characteristics of the MEDINA press releases

Characteristics	Description
Objective	Provide information about the MEDINA project in: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) A non – technical way so that the general audience: 2) A more technical way so that CISOs and compliance managers: can understand what continuous certification is, how MEDINA solves this issue and the benefits it brings.
Key Message/Content	Briefly present different key aspects of MEDINA
Target Stakeholder	General public, CSP's CISOs, CSP's compliance managers, auditors, CABs, NCCAs
Information Required & Level of Detail	Press releases usually describe the project, results and benefits with a language easy to understand by everyone.
Information Providers	All partners
Communication Methods	No specific configurations – Written in the languages of the consortium (German, Italian, Slovenian, Finish and Spanish) as well as in English
Activity Required for Production & Delivery	Partners' networks. Online media plus the website.
Frequency & Timing	2 per country in the project
Feedback and Follow Up Activity	Feedback from readers

4.2.4 Blog posts

MEDINA projects finds Blog posts a useful method to deliver the key result to various targets. In particular, general public will freely access and read the brief findings of the key aspects of the project.

The MEDINA blog¹³ has a twofold goal, as explained before. On one hand, it aims at explaining, in an easy way, the different activities that are being carried out in the project, in a short, focused way. The goal of this is to attract interest. On the other hand, it aims to make use of that content to generate leads and convert them into longer-term visitors, that is, make visitors to want to

¹³ <https://www.medina-project.eu/blog-timeline>

know more about the project, and inviting them to read other posts, browse the deliverables, videos and the like.

The blog posts will help MEDINA project to be recognized by the continuous certification and automated monitoring fields.

The following table present the overview related to blog posts. Moreover, marketing efforts are supported by blog posts that will be published in the NIXU blog¹⁴ <https://www.nixu.com/insights#nixu-blog> at regular intervals (two-weekly).

Table 11. Main characteristics of the MEDINA blog posts

Characteristics	Description
Objective	Provide information about different aspects of MEDINA. The content is written by partners, one partner at a time, and the content is freely decided by them. Since the expertise and background of the partners and team partners, as well as their role in the project is so different, the blog posts will deal with different issues on which MEDINA focuses on. For instance, one of the partners may describe the challenges of their use case, while another partner may write about the methodology to extract generic technical and organizational measures or about the collaboration with NIST OSCAL. The goal of the blog posts is mainly to position the project in the continuous certification and automated monitoring fields.
Key Message/Content	Briefly present different key aspects of MEDINA
Target Stakeholder	General public, CSP's CISOs, CSP's compliance managers, auditors, CABs, NCCAs
Information Required & Level of Detail	Blog posts will be on the MEDINA website and will usually describe the project, results and benefits with a language easy to understand by everyone. In addition, blogs can also be released on partners' websites as well as other sources such as reddit or medium.
Information Providers	All partners
Communication Methods	No specific configurations – Written in English
Activity Required for Production & Delivery	MEDINA's dedicated blog section.
Frequency & Timing	Every two weeks
Feedback and Follow Up Activity	Feedback from readers

4.2.5 Project newsletters

MEDINA consortium realizes that the newsletters will be vital to share the important news relate to the project to general public. Project newsletters will include the key achievements

¹⁴ <https://www.nixu.com/insights#nixu-blog>

accomplished by the partners as well as main activities related the project. The following table shows the highlighted information regarding the project newsletters.

Table 12. Main characteristics of the MEDINA newsletters

Characteristics	Description
Objective	Provide key activities and achievements of the project
Key Message/Content	Highlight the major outcomes, the most relevant activities, meetings and events, as well as future work.
Target Stakeholder	General public
Information Required & Level of Detail	Most important activities, major achievements, in some cases referencing blog entries, where these aspects will have been already reported.
Information Providers	All partners.
Communication Methods	English.
Activity Required for Production & Delivery	Gather content from previous posts, for instance. Online
Frequency & Timing	Yearly
Feedback and Follow Up Activity	Feedback from readers

4.2.6 White papers

White paper helps reader to understand MEDINA tools and proposed solutions. MEDINA project aims at writing at least three white papers that are mainly produced by NIXU. The following shows the target of white papers and its focus:

- Auditor Communities (e.g., ISACA) – Scientific/Technical paper
- Cloud Communities (e.g., CSA) - Scientific/Technical paper
- Cybersecurity Communities (e.g., OWASP) - Scientific/Technical paper
- Whitepaper describing NIXU's planned Proof of Concept implementation

White papers will be distributed through various media channels including pre-defined and created MEDINA channels, e.g., Twitter or LinkedIn.

Table 13. Main characteristics of the MEDINA white papers

Characteristics	Description
Objective	Provide a persuasive essay that uses facts and logic to promote Medina Platform for CSPs
Key Message/Content	Key messages for white papers are linked to the Key results delivered from auditors' perspective and experiences gained from Proof of Concept implementation.
Target Stakeholder	Auditor communities, Cloud Communities, Cybersecurity Communities
Information Required & Level of Detail	Information is needed from all partners regarding the key deliverables and results. Level of detail needs to be enough to provide 5-6 pages of essay.

Characteristics	Description
Information Providers	All partners.
Communication Methods	English.
Activity Required for Production & Delivery	Study of similar whitepapers, interview of partners. Delivery via twitter, blog posts & other social media tools
Frequency & Timing	1 whitepaper / Year
Feedback and Follow Up Activity	Feedback from readers via social media channels

4.2.7 Project showcases

Project showcases in the context of MEDINA are videos, mainly demo videos, showing the functionality of the various tools developed in the project.

Table 14. Main characteristics of the MEDINA project showcases

Characteristics	Description
Objective	Demonstrate how the tools of MEDINA work, both in a stand-alone way as well as integrated.
Key Message/Content	Highlight the different functionalities that the tools have and the competitive advantage with respect to tools in the market (if there exists any), as well as the benefits that they bring to any CSP, auditor or CAB that would be using it.
Target Stakeholder	CSPs, CISOs, compliance managers, auditors, CABs, NCCA
Information Required & Level of Detail	Purpose of the tool, what it can be used for, the different functionalities and steps that the potential user needs to execute, the benefits.
Information Providers	All tool owners.
Communication Methods	Video with English subtitles.
Activity Required for Production & Delivery	Record the screen. Video on MEDINA's Youtube channel.
Frequency & Timing	Whenever releases are brought out.
Feedback and Follow Up Activity	Feedback from viewers.

4.2.8 Social media and digital strategy

4.2.8.1 Digital Strategy

A digital strategy is the process of identifying and articulating messages on digital media with the objective of increasing the competitive advantage of an organization. As Boston Consulting Group states: *“a smart digital strategy, like [a] traditional business strategy, is about making*

wise investment choices to maximize competitive advantage, growth, profit, and value—and then implementing with discipline”¹⁵.

There is almost no literature available for the creation of a digital strategy for projects like MEDINA, as the existing sources mainly focus on companies and products. However, since the final result of the implementation of MEDINA will be a product, or better, a proof of concept, the digital strategy explained next will be an adaptation of a digital strategy for a product.

In the case of a product digital strategy, the focus is business to business rather than business to consumer, which calls for the development and use of what it is called Inbound Marketing.

Inbound marketing is a strategy that takes from pull marketing principles to create awareness and attract leads. It is mainly focused on three pillars:

- SEO (Search Engine Optimisation): search engine positioning or optimisation.
- Content Marketing: web, blogs, videos, webinars, infographics, documentation generated from the project activities, etc.
- Social Media marketing: networking.

The challenge here is to make these pillars work in an integrated way, where all actions and techniques used are combined in the right way enhancing thereof the reputation of MEDINA and achieving a higher visibility online. The figure below shows the elements that are critical for a successful inbound marketing strategy. The blog, newsletter and website have already been discussed in previous sections of this document. The social networks and the use of analytics tools are explained next in this same section.

Figure 1. Elements of Inbound Marketing used in MEDINA (adapted from <https://sendpulse.com/>)

As mentioned above, inbound marketing pursues a pull strategy, which seeks to get leads in a natural way rather than being ‘aggressive’, in what it is often considered outbound marketing. An easy example to understand the difference is the use of banners on websites (outbound marketing) vs an infographic (inbound).

Another key aspect in a digital strategy is the leads qualification. Lead qualification is the process of categorising a qualified sales or marketing lead as a customer who has been contacted and has engaged with the sales and marketing team, and so is further along the sales process than

¹⁵ <https://www.bcg.com/publications/2019/five-rules-digital-strategy.aspx>

other leads¹⁶. In the case of MEDINA, the objective of lead qualification is to understand what the interest of the visitors is. There are several questions that will have to be answered:

- Is it the results (deliverables), the blog posts, or others that attract leads?
- Where do the visitors come from? This is important due to the scope of the project (European certification scheme(s))
- How much time do they spend on MEDINA's website?

All three key questions are part of MEDINA's KPIs and will be measured through the use of Google Analytics.

The inbound methodology to be used in MEDINA is an adaptation of the common inbound marketing one with four steps: Attract – Convert – Close – Delight. While the phases remain the same, the tools used, and the approach are slightly different. This is explained next.

1. **Attract visitors:** the main objective is to attract (qualified) traffic to the website by means of:
 - i. Social networks: sharing relevant content for the different target groups, with content both generated inside and outside of MEDINA
 - ii. Blog posts: where team members post frequent entries commenting different aspects of the project. Blog entries are a good way to convey information to a large audience and provide several benefits in what respect to SEO and organic leads.
 - iii. Content strategy: the way in which the MEDINA project is presented to the visitors is important. Hence, details such as the benefits of the solution, the approach, the main results and access to project's deliverables are key to attract visitors.
2. **Convert:** once the audience has been attracted to the website, the time to convert visitors into lead has come. In commercial products the approach to this is to present forms, surveys, registering mechanisms to download e.g. whitepapers, and the landing page. In the case of a project like MEDINA the approach to be followed will be to understand what it is happening with the landing page, the blogs and the different microsites that are part of the website.
3. **Close:** seek to turn those qualified visitors into potential clients. In Commercial products this phase is often performed through emails campaign, use of CRMs and the like. Since MEDINA has decided not to store any personal data coming from the visitors to the website, the only way in which the project has for this phase is the interaction of the project with the audience through the social networks.
4. **Delight:** in commercial products, this phase is related to the automation of the tasks from the close phase, and through a regular interaction with the visitors through conversations in the light of future collaborations. In the case of a project like MEDINA, this approach needs to be revisited. There are several potential ways of doing this
 - i. Revisit MEDINA's website content in a frequent basis, keeping it always updated to reflect the real status of the project.
 - ii. Maintain the engagement through the publication of content of added value like for instance, the blog posts.
 - iii. Frequent publications on social networks that lead towards visits to the website.

¹⁶ <https://www.mycustomer.com/hr-glossary/lead-qualification#:~:text=Lead%20qualification%20is%20the%20process,sales%20process%20than%20other%20leads.>

4.2.8.2 Social media channels

In general, the digital strategy channel includes the **Website** and the **Blog**, but as these have been presented before in 4.2-Communication means, this section describes the main social media channels that will be used for the digital strategy.

Social networks: social networks allow for a more interactive communication. In MEDINA, the social networks used will be Twitter, Slideshare, LinkedIn and YouTube. The details are explained next.

Twitter: @medinaprojectEU

URL: <https://twitter.com/MedinaprojectEU>

Twitter will be used both for content generated inside the project as well as outside the project. The topics will revolve around security and certification. MEDINA will also follow relevant accounts on the topics.

The goal is to attract leads and visitors and create awareness of the project. Most published tweets will be supported with multimedia content in order to achieve the above. As a good practice to generate leads, whenever a post is published on the website, a Tweet announcing it will be published. This will help the project spread the word thanks to retweets and likes.

The hashtags to be used are: #EUCyberAct, #EUCS, #cloudsecurity, #cloudsecuritycertification, #automatedmonitoring.

Slideshare

URL: <https://www.slideshare.net/MEDINAContinuousclou>

The SlideShare account has been set up to share the presentations that the project has done in different events such as conferences, exhibitions and so on. These presentations are often rather technical.

YouTube

URL: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UClvJMKwz1cGfH3OS67k2A7Q>

The goal of the YouTube channel is to showcase videos coming from demos of the tools, participations in recorded events, promotional videos and so on.

4.3 Communication assessment and evaluation

In order to be able to continuously update and improve the communication strategy, a monitoring activity is necessary. This monitoring involves all communication channels described above on a monthly basis.

The tools used for the monitoring will be Google analytics, Twitter analytics (in its free version) and the dissemination monthly report sheet that the project has created (see Appendix).

As in dissemination, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been defined to assess the results obtained from different kinds of communication channels. These KPIs will be reported in the successive Dissemination and Communication Reports (D7.4 and D7.5) at M18 and M36, and are gathered in the next table.

Table 15. Communication KPIs (source: DoA)

Diss. tool	KPI	Objective	Contingency plans	Tool used
MEDINA website	Yearly visits	>1,700	Promoting the website through other channels (especially in social networks).	Google analytics
	Duration of visits	More than 2 min. for 40% of users	Re-organize the website to make it easier to find relevant items. Upload more attractive content.	Google analytics
	Monthly downloads: Posters, flyers Public reports	35 50	Promoting the website and the downloadable material through other channels (especially in social networks).	To be defined
	References from external web pages	20 (excluding partner webs)	Contact more stakeholders and initiatives to agree on the promotion of the site.	Manual / Conversion rates by Google Analytics
Twitter Feed	Number of followers (new) Number of Tweets (new) Number of following profiles (new) Number of likes (new) Impressions(new)	>200 followers >700 >200 >600 >5000	Control and encourage the publication of tweets, depending on the phase of development and implementation these may be monthly, weekly or even daily at peak milestones.	Twitter analytics (free version)
SlideShare (new)	Number of views	>300	Encourage partners to share their presentations	SlideShare analytics
YouTube	Number of views	>200	Encourage partners to share demo videos of their tools. Upload webinars (if allowed) where partners have participated	YouTube
Mass Media	Number of releases	2 per country in the project	The press releases will be delivered in English but also translated to the languages of the partners participating in the project.	Monthly dissemination report

Diss. tool	KPI	Objective	Contingency plans	Tool used
Blog posts	Number of entries	at least 6 every year	The blog posts will discuss the different technologies, solutions, problems faced or any other relevant novelty that has occurred in the project. This will be used as part of the inbound market strategy and will allow the social networks to bring more traffic to the project.	Monthly dissemination report
Reddit posts	Number of posts	> 6 posts per year (the author will address received comments or questions)	The consortium will raise awareness about the project with posts on Reddit in the following communities: r/cybersecurity (68.5k members), r/netsec (318k members), r/security (96.3k members).	Monthly dissemination report

5 Conclusions

This deliverable presented an in-depth strategy for dissemination, communication and training of the MEDINA project. All partners are involved in these activities either as contributors or leaders.

This deliverable explicitly outlines possible directions for dissemination of MEDINA results among scientific, industrial community and general public. Where it is possible, more concrete targets are established (e.g., possible publication venues or projects/organisations to cooperate with) to let the partners to focus their effort. The deliverable also tried to describe (as much as it possible at this stage of the project) concrete steps the project is planning to achieve the goals set for the dissemination and communication activities.

Although the outlined directions and targets are identified to cover most available possibilities for partners to disseminate project results, the partners will always look for additional ways to spread the knowledge about MEDINA.

This deliverable will be used as a guideline by the project participants to conduct the dissemination and communication to achieve the target key performance indicators (defined in DoA). MEDINA consortium will track the key performance indicators monthly to evaluate its progress towards achievement of the specified goals (reported in D7.4 and D7.5 Dissemination and Communication Report v1 and v2).

6 References

- [1] European Commission; "What is the difference between dissemination, exploitation and communication?," [Online]. Available: ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/faqs/faq-933.html.
- [2] MEDINA Consortium, "Description of Action - Annex 1 - GA 952633.," 2020.
- [3] MEDINA Consortium; "D7.1 MEDINA website and brochure," 2021.

7 Appendix: Dissemination monthly report forms

7.1 List of Scientific publications

List of publications: planned and submitted but not yet accepted

Table 16. List of Scientific Publications

Title of the article	Event and publication (name, date, other info)	Name of author and Organisations

7.3 General and business publications

Everything that cannot be considered scientific. For instance, publication on the partners' websites, interviews on the media, featured articles on the media.

Table 18. List of General & Business Publications

Title	Link or reference	Date	Partner/Authors (organisations)

7.4 Events: Conferences, seminars, workshops and webinars

Table 19. List of events

Event	Date	Name and type of audience	Countries addressed	Size of audience	People attending

7.5 Blog posts

Table 20. Blog posts

Title of blog entry	Main author	Release Date

7.6 Collaboration & Cooperation with other projects, programmes, working groups, initiatives, etc.

We will describe here the projects with which we are collaborating, under which areas and topics, and the status.

Explanation symbols

	Collaboration has already started – concrete collaboration activities are reported
	Collaboration is envisioned but have not started yet
	Collaboration is not feasible Collaboration have started but could not be continued – concrete collaboration activities are not reported

Table 21. Collaboration with other projects

Project	Areas for collaboration	Remark	Status

7.7 Report of the collaboration & cooperation activities.

Here we will report the collaboration activities performed, date, main conclusions and action points.

Table 22. Collaboration activities

No.	Project(s) Name	Description of activity
1.		
2.		
3.		
4.		
5.		
6.		
7.		
8.		
9.		
10.		

7.8 Press Releases

Table 8. Other dissemination Activities

Type	Published in	Partner/Authors

7.9 Other Dissemination Activities

Keynotes, workshops, prizes.

Table 23. Other dissemination Activities

Type	Name & Comment	Partner/Authors	Link if appropriate

7.10 Teaching activities

Courses

Table 24. Courses

Title/Speaker	Venue	Date	Link if appropriate